
ON RELATED BINOMIAL HARMONIC IDENTITIES

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Abstract

We develop new closed form representation of a positive sum of reciprocal binomial coefficients and its alternating counterpart. We also identify new integral and hypergeometric representations for the binomial-harmonic number sums.

1. Introduction

In this paper we are interested in the closed form expressions of the two related binomial sums

$$S(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}},$$

and its alternating counterpart

$$A(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}}.$$

The results in this paper add to the literature and are sums that are not considered in the recently published research results of [1] and [2]. Moreover, the work in this paper generalizes and extends the work of [10]. First we recall some definitions of some special functions that will be useful throughout this paper. The Gamma function, for $z \in \mathbb{C}$, as given by Euler in integral form, is

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{z-1} dt, \quad \Re(z) > 0,$$

where the special case for $z \in \mathbb{N}$ reduces to, from the recurrence relation, $\Gamma(n+1) = n\Gamma(n) = n!$. The Pochhammer, or shifted factorial, is defined by $(\lambda)_{\nu} = \frac{\Gamma(\lambda+\nu)}{\Gamma(\lambda)}$.

¹Lovingly dedicated to Anthony Kara

The Beta function, or Euler integral of the first kind, is

$$B(z, w) = \int_0^1 t^{z-1} (1-t)^{w-1} dt = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(w)}{\Gamma(z+w)}, \Re(z) > 0, \Re(w) > 0.$$

Let

$$H_n = \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{1}{r} = \int_0^1 \frac{1-t^n}{1-t} dt = \gamma + \psi(n+1) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{j(j+n)}, \quad H_0 := 0$$

be the n th harmonic number, where γ denotes the Euler-Mascheroni constant, $H_n^{(m)} = \sum_{r=1}^n \frac{1}{r^m}$ is the m th order harmonic number, and $\psi(z)$ is the Digamma (or Psi) function defined by

$$\psi(z) := \frac{d}{dz} \{\log \Gamma(z)\} = \frac{\Gamma'(z)}{\Gamma(z)} \text{ and } \psi(1+z) = \psi(z) + \frac{1}{z}.$$

Moreover

$$\psi(z) = -\gamma + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n+z} \right).$$

A generalized hypergeometric function is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}_pF_q [z] &= {}_pF_q \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_q \end{matrix} \middle| z \right] = {}_pF_q [(a_p); (b_q) | z] \\ &= \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{(a_1)_n \dots (a_p)_n}{(b_1)_n \dots (b_q)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!} = \sum_{n \geq 0} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^p (a_j)_n}{\prod_{j=1}^q (b_j)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

for b_j non-negative integers or zero. When $p \leq q$, ${}_pF_q [z]$ converges for all complex values of z , ${}_pF_q [z]$ is an entire function. When $p > q + 1$, ${}_pF_q [z]$ converges for $z = 0$ unless it terminates, which it does when one of the parameters a_j is a negative integer, and hence ${}_pF_q [z]$ is a polynomial in z . When $p = q + 1$ the series converges in the unit disc $|z| < 1$, and also for $|z| = 1$ provided that $\Re \left(\sum_{j=1}^q b_j - \sum_{j=1}^p a_j \right) > 0$.

When $p = 2, q = 1$ we have the familiar Gauss hypergeometric function

$${}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} a, b \\ c \end{matrix} \middle| z \right] = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1}}{(1-zt)^a} dt,$$

where $|z| < 1, \Re(c-b) > 0$ and $\Re(b) > 0$. In the subsequent analysis we shall also employ the consecutive derivative operator of the inverse binomial,

$$\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn+j}{k}^{-1} \right),$$

and investigate the resulting binomial harmonic sum

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn + j}{k}^{-1} \right)$$

and its alternating counterpart

$$A^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn + j}{k}^{-1} \right).$$

The following lemma will be useful in the development of the main theorem.

Lemma 1. *Let $p(n)$ and $q(n)$ be polynomials in n where all the roots of $q(n)$ are simple. Assume no root of $q(n)$ is in $\mathbb{N}$ and let $\deg(p(n)) \leq \deg(q(n) - 2)$. Let $v_n = \frac{p(n)}{q(n)}$. Then*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} v_n = - \sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r \psi(\beta_r) \tag{2}$$

where

$$v_n = \frac{p(n)}{q(n)} = \sum_{r=1}^k \frac{\alpha_r}{n + \beta_r}. \tag{3}$$

Proof. From $v_n = \frac{p(n)}{q(n)}$ we have $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} v_n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{p(n)}{q(n)}$. By partial fraction expansion, $v_n = \sum_{r=1}^k \frac{\alpha_r}{n + \beta_r}$ since all the roots of $q(n)$ are simple. For the series $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} v_n$ to converge it suffices to have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n v_n = 0$, in which case $\sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r = 0$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} v_n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{r=1}^k \frac{\alpha_r}{n + \beta_r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r \left(\frac{1}{n + \beta_r} - \frac{1}{n + 1} \right) \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n + \beta_r} - \frac{1}{n + 1} \right) \\ &= - \sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r (\gamma + \psi(\beta_r)) \\ &= - \sum_{r=1}^k \alpha_r \psi(\beta_r) \end{aligned}$$

and the lemma is proved. □

2. Closed Form Summation

We now prove the following theorems.

Theorem 1. *Let $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, $j \in (-1, \infty)$ and $q \in \mathbb{R}^+$, then we have the novel representation*

$$S(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}} = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi\left(\frac{qk+1-r+j}{qk}\right). \tag{4}$$

The case $j = 0$ reduces to

$$S(0, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{qkn}{k}} = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi\left(\frac{qk+1-r}{qk}\right). \tag{5}$$

Also

$$S(0, k, q) = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \left(\begin{matrix} \psi\left(\frac{r-1}{qk}\right) \\ +\pi \cot\left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{qk}\right) \end{matrix} \right). \tag{6}$$

Proof. Consider the expansion,

$$\begin{aligned} S(j, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{k! (qkn-k+j)!}{(qkn+j)!} \\ &= k! \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\prod_{r=1}^k (qkn+j+1-r)} = k! \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(qkn+j+1-k)_k} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\prod_{r=1}^k \left(n+1 + \frac{qk+j+1-r}{qk}\right)}, \end{aligned}$$

where Pochhammer's symbol $(x)_n = \frac{\Gamma(x+n)}{\Gamma(x)}$. By partial fraction decomposition we have

$$S(j, k, q) = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n + \frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}} \right),$$

and applying Lemma 1 we conclude

$$S(j, k, q) = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi\left(\frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}\right)$$

and (4) follows. For $j = 0$ (5) follows. By the reflection formula of the Digamma function $\psi(1-z) = \psi(z) + \pi \cot \pi z$, then (6) follows. Utilizing the definition (1), for the hypergeometric function, we can write

$$S(j, k, q) = \frac{1}{\binom{kq+j}{k}} {}_{kq+1}F_{kq} \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{kq+j+1-k}{kq}, \frac{kq+j+2-k}{kq}, \dots, \frac{2kq+j-k}{kq}, 1 \\ \frac{kq+j+1}{kq}, \frac{kq+j+2}{kq}, \dots, \frac{2kq+j}{kq} \end{matrix} \middle| 1 \right].$$

□

We remark that in the interesting paper [10], Nimbran considers the representation of

$$\frac{1}{k!} S(0, k, 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(nk-k)!}{(nk)!},$$

for $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, in closed form and evaluates $S(0, k, 1)$ for $k = \{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12\}$. In particular $S(0, 2, 1) = \ln 2$ is listed in [7], $S(0, 3, 1) = \frac{\sqrt{3}\pi}{12} - \frac{1}{4} \ln 3$ and $S(0, 4, 1) = \frac{1}{4} \ln 2 - \frac{\pi}{24}$ are listed in [9]. Nimbran’s search of the literature yields no other evaluation of $S(0, k, 1)$ for $k \geq 5$ and then sets out to evaluate $S(0, k, 1)$ for $k = \{5, 6, 8, 10, 12\}$. Nimbran claims $S(0, 10, 1)$ is difficult to evaluate and finds it impossible to evaluate $S(0, k, 1)$ for any other values of k . Nimbran’s method of evaluating $S(0, k, 1)$ is indeed ingenious and relies on the representation

$$\ln p = \sum_{m \geq 1} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{p-1} \left(\frac{1}{mp+r-m} - \frac{1}{mp} \right) \right),$$

which is a generalization of an identity given by Euler in 1734 [6]. We therefore see that the representation (4) gives a general identity for $S(j, k, q)$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$. Also recently [11], using a generalized binomial theorem in terms of Bell polynomials, evaluates some sums involving inverse binomial coefficients. The same technique is also used to calculate a class of hypergeometric transformation formulas, hence, there is still interest in evaluating binomial sums.

The following corollary applies.

Corollary 1. *Let $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, $j \in (-1, \infty)$ and $q \in R^+$, then we have the representation*

$$T(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{2qkn+j}{k}} = \frac{1}{2q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi\left(\frac{2qk+1-r+j}{2qk}\right).$$

The case $j = 0$ reduces to

$$T(0, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{2qkn}{k}} = \frac{1}{2q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi\left(\frac{2qk+1-r}{2qk}\right).$$

Also

$$T(0, k, q) = \frac{1}{2q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \psi\left(\frac{r-1}{2qk}\right) \\ +\pi \cot\left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{2qk}\right) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Proof. The proof follows directly from Theorem 1. □

Now we investigate $A(j, k, q)$.

Theorem 2. Under the assumptions of Theorem 1,

$$\begin{aligned} A(j, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}} \\ &= \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \psi\left(\frac{2qk+1-r+j}{2qk}\right) \\ -\psi\left(\frac{qk+1-r+j}{qk}\right) \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The case $j = 0$ reduces to

$$A(0, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{\binom{qkn}{k}} = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \psi\left(\frac{2qk+1-r}{2qk}\right) \\ -\psi\left(\frac{qk+1-r}{qk}\right) \end{pmatrix}. \tag{8}$$

Also,

$$A(0, k, q) = \frac{1}{q} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \psi\left(\frac{r-1}{2qk}\right) - \psi\left(\frac{r-1}{qk}\right) \\ +\pi \cot\left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{2qk}\right) - \pi \cot\left(\frac{\pi(r-1)}{qk}\right) \end{pmatrix}. \tag{9}$$

Proof. We begin by noticing that

$$S(j, k, q) + A(j, k, q) = 2T(j, k, q),$$

from which $A(j, k, q)$ follows directly, as does $A(0, k, q)$. The identity (9) follows from an application of the Digamma reflection formula. Utilizing the definition (1), for the hypergeometric function, we can write

$$A(j, k, q) = -\frac{1}{\binom{kq+j}{k}} {}_{kq+1}F_{kq} \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{kq+j+1-k}{kq}, \frac{kq+j+2-k}{kq}, \dots, \frac{2kq+j-k}{kq}, 1 \\ \frac{kq+j+1}{kq}, \frac{kq+j+2}{kq}, \dots, \frac{2kq+j}{kq} \end{matrix} \middle| -1 \right].$$

□

Remark 1. The other notable case is for the situation of $j = qk$, from which we ascertain, in a straightforward manner, the following results:

$$S(qk, k, q) = S(0, k, q) - \frac{1}{\binom{qk}{k}},$$

$$A(qk, k, q) = -A(0, k, q) - \frac{1}{\binom{qk}{k}}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} S(qk, k, q) - A(qk, k, q) &= S(0, k, q) - A(0, k, q) \\ &= 2T(0, k, q). \end{aligned}$$

Example 1. Some examples follow:

$$S\left(j, k, \frac{1}{k}\right) = \frac{j+1}{(k-1) \binom{j+1}{k}},$$

$$S(2, 2, 6) = \frac{\pi}{6} - 1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \ln(\sqrt{3}-1) + \frac{\sqrt{3}+1}{6} \ln 2,$$

$$S\left(-\frac{1}{8}, 3, \frac{1}{4}\right) = \frac{496}{55} + 12 \ln 3, \quad T\left(\frac{3}{2}, 4, \frac{1}{4}\right) = 8\pi - \frac{64}{3},$$

$$T\left(0, 2, \frac{3}{4}\right) = \ln 3 - \frac{\sqrt{3}\pi}{9}, \quad T(4, 2, 3) = \frac{1}{2} \ln 2 - \frac{1}{4} \ln 3 + \frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{12\sqrt{3}}\pi - \frac{1}{6};$$

$$A(4, 3, 2) = \frac{2 - \sqrt{3}}{2\sqrt{3}}\pi - \frac{1}{4}, \quad A\left(-\frac{1}{2}, 2, 1\right) = -2\sqrt{2} \ln(\sqrt{2} + 1),$$

$$A\left(j, 2, \frac{1}{4p}\right) = 4p(H_{jp} - H_{jp-p} - (H_{2jp} - H_{2jp-2p})), \quad p \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

In the next section we give an extension to Theorem 1 by incorporating harmonic numbers to the sums $S(j, k, q)$, $A(j, k, q)$ and associating the sum with hypergeometric and integral representation.

3. Extension

We begin with the proof of the following Theorem.

Theorem 3. *Let the assumptions of Theorem 1 apply and let $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn + j}{k}^{-1} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Q^{(m)}(j, k, q)$$

$$= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}\right)$$
(10)

$$= \frac{m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+m+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} H_{\frac{1+j-r}{qk}}^{(m+1)}$$
(11)

where

$$Q^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn + j}{k}^{-1} \right).$$
(12)

Proof. From the identity (4) we differentiate both sides "m" times with respect to j so that,

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn + j}{k}^{-1} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Q^{(m)}(j, k, q)$$

$$= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}\right)$$

and (10) follows. From the known identity relating polygamma functions with harmonic numbers,

$$\psi^{(m)}(1+z) = (-1)^m m! \left(H_z^{(m+1)} - \zeta(1+m) \right),$$
(13)

we have

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \frac{m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+m+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} H_{\frac{1+j-r}{qk}}^{(m+1)}$$

since

$$\sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^r \binom{k-1}{r-1} = 0, \text{ for } k \geq 2,$$

and hence (11) follows. For completeness we detail some values of $Q^{(m)}(j, k, q)$:

$$Q^{(1)}(j, k) = \frac{1}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}} (H_{qkn+j-k} - H_{qkn+j})$$

and

$$Q^{(2)}(j, k, q) = \frac{1}{\binom{qkn+j}{k}} \left((H_{qkn+j} - H_{qkn+j-k})^2 + (H_{qkn+j}^{(2)} - H_{qkn+j-k}^{(2)}) \right).$$

Some more details on the function $Q^{(m)}(j, k, q)$ are given in the paper [13]. □

Next we investigate $A^{(m)}(j, k, q)$ as described below.

Theorem 4. *Let the assumptions of Theorem 1 apply and let $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then,*

$$A^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{qkn+j}{k}^{-1} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n Q^{(m)}(j, k, q) \tag{14}$$

$$= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2^m} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk+1+j-r}{2qk}\right) \\ -\psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}\right) \end{pmatrix} \tag{15}$$

$$= \frac{m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+m+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^m} H_{\frac{1+j-r}{2qk}}^{(m+1)} - H_{\frac{1+j-r}{qk}}^{(m+1)} \right), \tag{16}$$

where $Q^{(m)}(j, k, q)$ is given by (12).

Proof. From the identity (7) we differentiate both sides "m" times with respect to j so that,

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^{(m)}(j, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\left(\binom{qkn + j}{k} \right)^{-1} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n Q^{(m)}(j, k, q) \\
 &= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2^m} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk+1+j-r}{2qk}\right) \\ -\psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk+1+j-r}{qk}\right) \end{pmatrix},
 \end{aligned}$$

and (15) follows. From the known identity (13), relating polygamma functions with harmonic numbers, then

$$A^{(m)}(j, k, q) = \frac{m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+m+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \left(\frac{1}{2^m} H_{\frac{1+j-r}{2qk}}^{(m+1)} - H_{\frac{1+j-r}{qk}}^{(m+1)} \right)$$

since,

$$\sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^r \binom{k-1}{r-1} = 0, \text{ for } k \geq 2$$

and (16) is attained. □

The cases $j = 0$ and $j = kq$ are interesting and the results are given in the next corollary.

Corollary 2. For $j = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(m)}(0, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lim_{j \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\left(\binom{kqn + j}{k} \right)^{-1} \right) \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Q^{(m)}(0, k, q) \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m+1} m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \zeta(m+1) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^{k-1} (-1)^{r+k} \binom{k-1}{r} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk-r}{qk}\right). \tag{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $j = kq$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(m)}(kq, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lim_{j \rightarrow kq} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\left(\binom{kqn + j}{k} \right)^{-1} \right) \right) \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m} m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} (1 - \zeta(m+1)) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^{k-1} (-1)^{r+k} \binom{k-1}{r} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk-r}{qk}\right) \tag{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From (10) we have

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(0, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lim_{j \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{kqn + j}{k}^{-1} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(1 + \frac{1-r}{qk}\right). \end{aligned}$$

At $r = 1$, we notice that $\psi^{(m)}(1) = (-1)^{m+1} m! \zeta(m+1)$ and hence

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(0, k, q) &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m+1} m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} \zeta(m+1) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=2}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(1 + \frac{1-r}{qk}\right) \end{aligned}$$

and, making a change in the summation index, then (17) follows. For the case $j = qk$,

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(kq, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lim_{j \rightarrow kq} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{kqn + j}{k}^{-1} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk + 1 - r}{qk}\right). \end{aligned}$$

At $r = 1$, we notice that $\psi^{(m)}(2) = (-1)^m m! (1 - \zeta(m+1))$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(kq, k, q) &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m} m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} (1 - \zeta(m+1)) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=2}^k (-1)^{r+k+1} \binom{k-1}{r-1} \psi^{(m)}\left(2 + \frac{1-r}{qk}\right), \end{aligned}$$

and making a change in the summation index, then (18) follows. □

The following corollary refers to the $A^{(m)}(j, k, q)$, for the two special cases of $j = 0$ and $j = qk$.

Corollary 3. For $j = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} A^{(m)}(0, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \lim_{j \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{kqn + j}{k}^{-1} \right) \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Q^{(m)}(0, k, q) \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m+1} m! (1 - 2^m)}{q (2kq)^m} \zeta(m+1) \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$+ \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^{k-1} (-1)^{r+k} \binom{k-1}{r} \left(\frac{1}{2^m} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk-r}{2qk}\right) - \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{qk-r}{qk}\right) \right).$$

For $j = qk$,

$$\begin{aligned} A^{(m)}(kq, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \lim_{j \rightarrow kq} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{kqn+j}{k}^{-1} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{k+m} m!}{k^m q^{m+1}} (1 + (2^{-m} - 1) \zeta(m+1)) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{k^m q^{m+1}} \sum_{r=1}^{k-1} (-1)^{r+k} \binom{k-1}{r} \left(\frac{1}{2^m} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{3qk-r}{2qk}\right) - \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2qk-r}{qk}\right) \right). \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Proof. The proof follows the same pattern as the proof in the previous corollary. $\square$

Example 2. Some illustrative examples follow:

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(2)}(j, 3, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(H_{3qn+j} - H_{3qn+j-3})^2 + (H_{3qn+j}^{(2)} - H_{3qn+j-3}^{(2)})}{\binom{3qn+j}{3}} \\ &= -\frac{1}{9q^3} \left(\psi^{(2)}\left(\frac{j-2+3q}{3q}\right) - 2\psi^{(2)}\left(\frac{j-1+3q}{3q}\right) + \psi^{(2)}\left(\frac{j+3q}{3q}\right) \right), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(j, 2, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \binom{2qn+j}{2}^{-1} \\ &= \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \left(\psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2q+j}{2q}\right) - \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2q+j-1}{2q}\right) \right). \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

By the Leibniz rule of differentiation, we can also write,

$$S^{(m)}(j, 2, q) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{t=0}^m \frac{(-1)^m m!}{(2qn+j)^{t+1} (2qn+j-1)^{m-t+1}}.$$

Using the recurrence relation of the polygamma function,

$$\psi^{(m)}(1+z) = \psi^{(m)}(z) + \frac{(-1)^m m!}{z^{m+1}},$$

then from (21) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(m)}(j, 2, q) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{t=0}^m \frac{(-1)^m m!}{(2qn + j)^{t+1} (2qn + j - 1)^{m-t+1}} \\
 &= \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \left(\psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{j}{2q}\right) - \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{j-1}{2q}\right) \right) + 2(-1)^m m! \left(\frac{1}{j^{m+1}} - \frac{1}{(j-1)^{m+1}} \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

from which

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(4)}(4, 2, 6) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{t=0}^4 \frac{4!}{(12n + 4)^{t+1} (12n + 3)^{5-t}} \\
 &= \frac{125}{1728} \zeta(5) + \frac{(15 - 2\sqrt{3})}{46656} \pi^5 - \frac{781}{5184}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also have

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{(m)}(2q, 2, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lim_{j \rightarrow 2q} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{2qn + j}{2}^{-1} \right) \right) \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^m m!}{2^m q^{m+1}} (1 - \zeta(m + 1)) - \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{4q - 1}{2q}\right) \\
 &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{t=0}^m \frac{(-1)^m m!}{(2qn + 2q)^{t+1} (2qn + 2q - 1)^{m-t+1}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^{(m)}(0, 2, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \lim_{j \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{d^{(m)}}{dj^{(m)}} \left(\binom{2qn + j}{2}^{-1} \right) \right) \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^{m+1} m! (1 - 2^m)}{4^m q^{m+1}} \zeta(m + 1) - \frac{1}{4^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{4q - 1}{4q}\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{2q - 1}{2q}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^{(m)}(2q, 2, q) &= \frac{(-1)^m m! (1 + (2^m - 1) \zeta(m + 1))}{2^m q^{m+1}} - \frac{1}{4^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{6q - 1}{4q}\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{4q - 1}{2q}\right) \\
 &= 2 \sum_{t=0}^m \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+m} m!}{(2qn + 2q)^{t+1} (2qn + 2q - 1)^{m-t+1}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The expression $S^{(m)}(j, k, q)$ and $A^{(m)}(j, k, q)$ can also be represented in integral and hypergeometric form and for completeness the following is recorded.

Theorem 5. *Let the assumptions of Theorem 1 apply. Then,*

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = k \int_0^1 \frac{x^{kq+j-k} (1-x)^{k-1} \ln^m x}{1-x^{kq}} dx, \tag{22}$$

$$A^{(m)}(j, k, q) = -k \int_0^1 \frac{x^{kq+j-k} (1-x)^{k-1} \ln^m x}{1+x^{kq}} dx. \tag{23}$$

Proof. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} S(j, k, q) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\binom{kqn+j}{k}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(kqn+j-k+1)\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(kqn+j+1)} \\ &= k \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} B(k, kqn-k+j+1), \end{aligned}$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function and $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the beta function. Now

$$S(j, k, q) = k \int_0^1 \frac{x^j (1-x)^{k-1}}{x^k} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^{kq})^n dx.$$

Differentiating m times with respect to j results in

$$S^{(m)}(j, k, q) = k \int_0^1 \frac{x^{kq+j-k} (1-x)^{k-1} \ln^m x}{1-x^{kq}} dx,$$

and hence (22). The result (23) follows by the same analysis. □

Remark 2. It is straightforward to see, from (17), (22) and (23), that

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(m)}(2q, 2, q) &= \frac{(-1)^m m!}{2^m q^{m+1}} (1 - \zeta(m+1)) - \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{4q-1}{2q}\right) \\ &= 2 \int_0^1 \frac{x^{4q-2} (1-x) \ln^m x}{1-x^{2q}} dx, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A^{(m)}(2q, 2, q) &= \frac{(-1)^m m! (1 + (2^m - 1) \zeta(m+1))}{2^m q^{m+1}} - \frac{1}{4^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{6q-1}{4q}\right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2^m q^{m+1}} \psi^{(m)}\left(\frac{4q-1}{2q}\right) \\ &= -2 \int_0^1 \frac{x^{4q-2} (1-x) \ln^m x}{1+x^{2q}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Many other examples of binomial sums, harmonic number sums, integral representations and hypergeometric summation are available in [3], [4], [5], [8], [12], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18] and [19].

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